

CONCEPT OF MARMA IN AYURVEDA: A LITERARY REVIEW***¹Dr. Jyoti Baburao Patil**¹Assistant Professor (Rachana Sharir), Dr. N. J. Paulbudhe Ayurved College and Hospital, Narayandoho, Dist.-Ahilyanagar, Maharashtra.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Jyoti Baburao Patil**

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is the science of life. *Ayurveda* deals with the prevention as well as principles regarding disease cured. In present era the need of *Ayurveda* and importance of *Ayurveda* science is increases day by day. *Ayurveda* is not only a system of medicine in the conventional sense of curing disease. It is also a way of life that teaches us how to maintain and protect mental and physical health and achieve longevity. In *Ayurveda* various unique concepts are explained such as *Nadi pariksha*, *Marma*, *Viddha karma*, etc. In which the concept of *Marma* is very unique & as well as important for *Chikitsaka*. *Marma* are important for *Vyadhi Chikitsa*. They are classified in various types according to *Panchabhautika* dominance and various factors. Every *Chikitsaka* has knowledge about *Marmas* for avoidance of injury to them. Which is helpful for *Chikitsa*. It is also known as '*Jeevanadhara*'.

KEYWORDS: *Marma*, *Ayurveda*, Conceptual study.**INTRODUCTION**

Marmas are found by the confluence of 5 important elements or structures of the body namely; *Mamsa*, *Sira*, *Snayu*, *Asthi* and *Sandhi*.^[1] Carefully observing this are the main structures which make up the bulk anatomy of the body. The *Marmas* are 107^[2] in numbers as per *Acharya Sushruta*.

They are composed of all five basic anatomical components^[3]; *Sira marma* – 41, *Mamsa marma* – 11, *Snayu marma* – 27, *Asthi marma* – 8 & *Sandhi marma* – 20.

Concept of Marma**Classification of Marma****A. On the basis of the qualities, Marmas are of 3 types**

1. *Agneya*
2. *Saumya*
3. *Vayavya*

B. On the basis of surgical importance, it is of 5 types^[4]

1. *Sadya Pranahara Marma* : 19 in numbers, *Agneya* and Fatal period within 7 days.
2. *Kalanta Pranahara Marma* : 33 in numbers, *Saumya* and Fatal period 15 days to 1 month.

3. *Rujakara Marma* : 8 in numbers, *Agneya* & *Vayavya*. Create intense pain.
4. *Vishalyaghna Marma* : 3 in numbers, *Vayavya*, Fatality depends on Specific trauma.
5. *Vaikalya kara Marma* : 44 in numbers and *Saumya*.

C. Considering the sites and location of Marma based on Shadangas of the body

1. Head & neck – 37
2. *Ura* and *Udara pradesha* – 12
3. *Prushtha* – 14
4. 11 in each of the extremities

Physiological basis of Marma

- *Marma* points are the seats of *Dvadasha Prana*^[6] – *Soma*, *Vayu*, *Teja*, *Satva*, *Raja*, *Tama*, *Pancha Gyanendriya* and *Jeevatma*. It is also known as '*Jeevashthana*' or '*Pranayatna*'.
- Any injury to these vital parts may leads to death, loss of function, intense pain and loss of sensation.
- This concept of *Marma*, is conceived martial arts, acupuncture and acupressure.
- According to *Sushruta*, due to injury to *Mamsa marma*, there is loss of sensation of touch. Hence local anesthesia can be produced by irritating the *Mamsa Marma*.

Scope and indication

- In traumatic nerve damage; Monoplegia, Paraplegia, Hemiplegia.
- In diseases of Nerves and Brains: Mono-neuropathy, Poly-neuropathy, Brain atrophy, Parkinson's disease, Dementia.
- In Orthopedic disorders: Vertebral disc prolapsed, Spondylosis, Sciatica, Scoliosis, Osteoarthritis, Osteoporosis.
- To reduce pain of nerves, muscles, bones and joints.
- To produce anesthesia during surgical interventions.
- To improve the function of body by achieving the homeostasis of body humors.
- To improve deformed parts of the body into Healthy state.

Etymological aspect of Marma^[6]

- In *Buddha* period, the science of *Marma* was transformed in the form of different martial arts.
- In *Siddha* system – the *Marma* therapy is a form of treatment of *Parna* by connecting life forces like *Shiva* and *Shakti*.
- *Sushruta* was the first person who provides conceptual frame work to the practice of the surgery and *Marma*.
- It is untouched and clinically unopened area of *Ayurvedic* therapeutics.
- It is the oldest treasure of *Ayurvedic* medicine or surgery since vedic period.
- *Riga veda* speaks of using protective coverings to protect these *Marmas*.
- The term *Marma* first time came in *Atharvaveda*.
- *Mahabharata* contains many references of *Marma* therapy.
- In that days it is the important tools for Soldiers and Kings.
- Its therapeutic approach was strictly prohibited to the general public due to its acute effectiveness and due to misuses.
- *Acharya Agastya* is the first who codifying the 107 nerve centers or *Marma* points in South India.
- These 107 vital points are used in Indian acupuncture, acupressure and martial in the tradition of Kerala.

Effect of Marma injury^[7]**A) Sadya Pranahara Marma**

- When this *marma* get injured, death occurs in 7 days.
- Other symptoms of injury include – loss of perception of sense organs (*Indriyartheshu Asamprapti*), perversion in the activities of mind and intellect / cognitive functions (*Manobuddhi Viparyaya*), different types of severe pains and quick death.
- These *Marmas* are predominantly composed of *Agni mahabhuta* and by the effect of *Agni*, this *marmas* cause death in quick time.

B) Kalantara Pranahara Marma

- When these *marmas* get injured, there is gradual death. The person may die within 15 days or one month.
- This happens due to the unique composition of this *marmas*. This *marmas* are made of *Agni* and *Jala* elements. *Agni* acts and effects quickly and *soma* acts and effects slowly.
- Due to the association of water element, the death is slow.
- Other associated symptoms are Emaciation or depletion of tissues (*Dhatu kshaya*) and pain due to Emaciation (*Kshayaja Vedana*).
- An injury in the surrounding area of *Sadya Pranahara Marmas* may lead to effect on *Kalantara Pranahara marmas* also.

C) Vaikalyakara Marma

- They are predominantly formed by *Soma guna*. These *marmas* on getting injured causes deformity.
- *Soma or jala dhatu* by the virtue of its stability and cold qualities protects the *Pranas* located in the *marmas*. Therefore these *marmas* do not cause death on injury but surely cause deformities.
- Severe injury may cause death. Proper treatment by an efficient physician will limit the injury to cause deformity but not the death.

Diseases in Marma sites

Among the diseases caused in various directions or places in the body. *Marmasthi*, *Sandhigata* are considered to be difficult to handle. They are also considered as '*Madhyama roga marga*'. Among the tissues, *Asthi*, *Majja* and *Shukra* are considered as *Marma*. The diseases occurring to them are also difficult to treat.

DISCUSSION

In *Ayurveda Marma* is one the unique and important concept described. It is very important in present era for the *Chikitsa* and Diagnosis of disease. *Marma* are the half part of the *Shalya tantra* in *Ayurveda* science. Various types of *Marmas* are explained in *Ayurveda*. In which if some *marma* get injured then it causes death, deformity or loss of functions in the body. It is very important aspect as per *Shalya tantra*. Knowledge of *Marma* are helpful while performing Surgery or any procedure. In *Charka samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hrudaya* etc all *Acharyas* explained the total numbers of *marma* was 107. *Sushruta* states that if *Aaghata* happens anywhere in the body and it leads to death of an individual then it is known as '*Marma*'. It is formed by the elements like *Asthi*, *Majja*, *Sandhi*, *Snayu*. They are correlated with each other. So therefore any one get injured from this they causes injury or damage to other parts also. *Acharya Vagbhata* mentioned the *Marma Viddha lakshanas*. They are *Guruta*, *Sammhoha*, *Murccha*, *Shwasa* etc. The main three *Marmas* are *Shira*, *Hrudaya* and *Basti*. If *Aaghata* or injury happens to this *marmas* then it leads to death. So therefore study of

marmas are very important aspect for physician and it is need of today's era in *Ayurveda*.

CONCLUSION

The concept of *marma* is important aspect as its damage directly causes death of a person. So therefore its aspect for clinical practice is more important. *Acharya Sushruta* states that the *Marma* is surrounded by the elements like *Snayu, asthi, sandhi, Mamsa, sira* and its connection connects with the *Prana* of a person. *Sushruta* described *marmas* according to body parts, body regions. He mentioned that *marmas* present all over the body and its injury causes deformity, loss of function or death. So therefore concept of *marma* is important.

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